

A NOVEL APPROACH FOR IMPACT MITIGATION USING MASS NEGATIVITY CONCEPT OF METACOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this work, a novel approach for impact mitigation and protection by using the mass negativity concept of metacomposites is introduced. The application is to build a protection system that can mitigate impact loads and attenuate blast wave. There is an increasing use of improvised explosive devices (IEDs) in terrorist and insurgent activities. Exposure to blast is becoming more frequent. Blast related injuries can be inflicted at various levels. Primary blast injury results from blast wave-induced changes in atmospheric pressure, causing organs and tissues to rupture due to shearing and stretching at different rates. Secondary blast injury results from objects put in motion by the blast wind impacting a person. Tertiary blast injury results from a person being blown into solid objects by the blast wind. This paper deals with the protection system against primary blast injury by mitigating blast wave. Shear and stress waves from the primary blast could potentially cause traumatic brain injury (TBI) directly. Very often no external physical injuries are detected in the affected victims, but serious damages are inflicted internally, particularly to the brain where neurological effects can be slow to appear. In this paper, the concept of elastic metamaterials is firstly introduced by presenting the unique property of negative effective mass density through simple analytical mass-in-mass models. Next, the impact wave attenuation and blast wave mitigation capability of the metacomposites are demonstrated using computational simulation. Finally, practical ways to design and manufacture metacomposites protection system with negative effective mass density are proposed and presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

Soldiers in warzone continue to face the peril of impact blast-wave caused by detonations and improvised explosive devices (IEDs). The impact of blast-wave propagation is so lethal to human health that although no external physical injuries are detected in the affected soldiers, serious damages are inflicted internally, particularly to the brain where neurological effects can be slow to appear [1]. It has been postulated that blast waves ripple through the victim's torso up into the brain through major blood vessels [2]. In recent times, the exposure to blast threat extends beyond warzones. Civilians now encounter the increased risk to terrorist attack by the use of explosive dangerous bombs, as well as IEDs. As such, it is important to develop materials that would absorb or reflect the full range of blast-wave frequencies generated by an explosion. It is critical to find ways for material, not only to stop projectiles like shrapnel or bullets, but also to effectively attenuate the injurious effects of incoming blast and shock wave.

Researchers have been investigating ways to mitigate shock and blast waves by using different forms of materials and structures. By far, the principal of blast-wave mitigation is either using deformation of materials to absorb energy [3], which results in vast material damage, or using anti-momentum principle to oppose the incoming blast-wave, which requires somewhat complex structures [4, 5]. Moreover, these concepts cannot be designed to tailor attenuation of specific frequency ranges, or cover the full range of blast-wave frequencies.

In this paper, we investigate the use of elastic metamaterials to mitigate blast-wave and attenuate stress wave propagation [6]. Metamaterials represent a novel and emerging field in materials engineering, and are characterized by the fact that they possess exceptional material properties not commonly found in natural materials. These material properties are enacted, not due to chemical

composition, but by specially designed man-made microstructures. Metamaterials originally started in the field of electromagnetic waves where researchers investigated negative electrical permittivity, negative magnetic permeability and negative refractive index [7, 8]. Motivated by the mathematical analogy between acoustic and electromagnetic waves, the counterpart acoustic metamaterials are recently explored [9-12]. This new branch of acoustic metamaterials, also known as mechanical or elastic metamaterials, consists of tailored microstructures that exhibit unusual mechanical properties such as negative effective modulus and/or negative effective mass density [9-12]. This paper aims to employ the effective negative mass density concept of acoustic/elastic metamaterials for blast-wave impact mitigation. We explore the use of metacomposites to build a protection system that can mitigate dynamic loads and attenuate blast wave. Firstly, the concept of elastic metamaterials is introduced by presenting the unique property of negative effective mass density through simple analytical mass-in-mass models. Secondly, the impact wave attenuation and blast wave mitigation capability of the metacomposites are demonstrated using computational simulation. Finally, practical ways to design and manufacture metacomposites protection system with negative effective mass density are proposed and presented.

2 ANALYTICAL MASS-IN-MASS MODELS

The concept of negative effective mass density can be achieved by using a mass-in-mass unit microstructure [11, 13]. Figure 1 shows the microstructure of a single-resonator spring-mass system. The outer unit cell has a mass m_1 and displacement u_1 , while the internal resonator has a mass m_2 and displacement u_2 . The internal resonator is coupled to the outer mass by a linear spring of stiffness k_2 . By considering the free body diagrams of the masses m_1 and m_2 , we can obtain the equations of forces as

$$m_1 \ddot{u}_1 = F + k_2(u_2 - u_1) \quad (1)$$

$$m_2 \ddot{u}_2 = k_2(u_1 - u_2) \quad (2)$$

Assuming that the displacement of masses follow harmonic wave behaviour, similar to that of the applied force F , we have

$$F(t) = F_0 e^{-i\omega t} \quad (3)$$

$$u_\gamma(x, t) = \hat{u}_\gamma e^{-i\omega t} \quad (4)$$

whereby $\gamma = 1, 2$ in this case.

By solving the above equations, we can simplify the relation to

$$0 = F_0 + \left(m_1 + \frac{\omega_2^2 m_2}{\omega_2^2 - \omega^2}\right) \omega^2 \hat{u}_1 \quad (5)$$

where $\omega_2 = \sqrt{\frac{k_2}{m_2}}$ is the local resonance frequency of the internal resonator mass m_2 .

Figure 1: Microstructure of single-resonator spring-mass system and its effective mass.

To obtain an effective mass behaviour of the microstructure, the following equation must be satisfied

$$F_O = -m_{eff}\omega^2\hat{u}_1 \quad (6)$$

Physically, this means that the motion of outer mass, m_1 is similar to that of an equivalent effective mass, m_{eff} , depicted schematically in Figure 1. Solving equations (5) and (6), we attain the effective mass of the microstructure as

$$m_{eff} = m_1 + \frac{\omega_2^2 m_2}{\omega_2^2 - \omega^2} \quad (7)$$

It is clear that the effective mass, m_{eff} , is frequency ω dependent. Further manipulation of the equation gives the normalized effective mass, m_{eff}/m_{st} as follows

$$\frac{m_{eff}}{m_{st}} = 1 + \frac{\theta}{1 + \theta} \left[\frac{(\omega / \omega_2)^2}{1 - (\omega / \omega_2)^2} \right] \quad (8)$$

where $m_{st} = m_1 + m_2$ is the static mass of the microstructure and $\theta = \frac{m_2}{m_1}$ is the ratio of internal

mass m_2 to that of the outer mass m_1 .

From equation (8), it is obvious that the function of m_{eff}/m_{st} against ω/ω_2 is dependent only on a single parameter θ . ω/ω_2 simply represents the normalized operating frequency of the system. Plots of m_{eff}/m_{st} against ω/ω_2 with varying θ values are presented in Figure 2. It is evident that a narrow band gap region exists where the effective mass becomes negative near to the local resonance frequency of the internal mass m_2 , when $\omega/\omega_2=1$. It has been shown in earlier work that this negative effective mass region corresponds to the band gap region of the dispersion curve when wave propagation is

considered [11]. Moreover, since the wave speed is given as $v = \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho}}$, this means that wave cannot

propagate in elastic solids when effective mass density is negative. This also implies that stress wave cannot be transmitted through the metamaterial structure when the frequency ω is near to the local resonance frequency of the internal resonator ω_2 . The negative effective mass density arises from the negative total momentum of the unit cell with positive velocity fields due to local resonance, which has been confirmed by experimental study [14]. It has been shown that such system is capable of attenuating wave propagation. However, one major limitation of the single-resonator model is that the negative effective mass exhibits only within a very narrow band gap region, specifically near the resonance frequency of the internal resonator. This limits the use of such system in applications where broad band gap is required, like wide frequency range in blast/shock wave.

Figure 2: Plot of normalized effective mass m_{eff}/m_{st} against normalized operating frequency ω/ω_2 .

A dual-resonator microstructure model is recently proposed [15]. The dual-resonator model is basically a mass-in-(mass-in-mass) unit, having two coupled internal resonators. The internal resonator is mass m_2 , the middle mass is m_1 and the outer mass is m_3 . The analytical model of this microstructure can be similarly derived by considering the equations of motions for the three masses and equating the behaviour of the entire microstructure as an effective mass m_{EFF} . The equations of forces considering the free body diagrams of the masses give the following equations

$$m_3\ddot{u}_3 = F + k_1(u_1 - u_3) \quad (9)$$

$$m_1\ddot{u}_1 = k_2(u_2 - u_1) + k_1(u_3 - u_1) \quad (10)$$

$$m_2\ddot{u}_2 = k_2(u_1 - u_2) \quad (11)$$

Using the same assumptions as the single-resonator model, we can solve and manipulate the equations to give the normalized effective mass, m_{EFF}/m_{ST} of the dual-resonator model as below:

$$\frac{m_{EFF}}{m_{ST}} = \frac{\theta_1}{\theta_1 + \theta_3 + \theta_1\theta_3} + \frac{\theta_3}{\theta_1 + \theta_3 + \theta_1\theta_3} \left\{ \frac{1 + \theta_1 - (\omega/\omega_2)^2}{\left[1 - (\omega/\omega_2)^2\right] \left[1 + \delta_1 - (\delta_1/\theta_1)(\omega/\omega_2)^2\right] - \delta_1} \right\} \quad (12)$$

where $m_{ST} = m_1 + m_2 + m_3$ is the static mass of the microstructure, $\omega_2 = \sqrt{\frac{k_2}{m_2}}$ is the local resonance frequency of internal mass m_2 , $\theta_1 = \frac{m_2}{m_1}$ is the ratio of internal mass m_2 to that of the middle

mass m_1 , $\theta_3 = \frac{m_2}{m_3}$ is the ratio of internal mass m_2 to that of the outer mass m_3 , and $\delta_1 = \frac{k_2}{k_1}$ is the ratio

of spring stiffness connecting the internal mass k_2 to that of the middle mass k_1 . It is clear from equation (12) that the function of m_{EFF}/m_{ST} against ω/ω_2 is dependent on three parameters, namely: θ_1 , θ_3 and δ_1 . Their effects are further described in [6]. By combining the effects of all 3 parameters (θ_1 , θ_3 and δ_1), we can specifically tailor an acoustic/elastic metamaterial to achieve wave attenuation over designed band gap regions.

3 COMPUTATIONAL SIMULATION OF IMPACT WAVE ATTENUATION AND BLAST WAVE MITIGATION

3.1 Impact Wave Attenuation

A one-dimensional spring-mass lattice system is constructed as shown schematically in Figure 3(a). The masses are $m_L=0.03$ kg, and the springs have stiffness of $k_L=1 \times 10^7$ N/m. The first 20 unit cells are considered Medium 1 and the last 20 unit cells are denoted as Medium 2. The middle 10 unit cells represent the Metamaterial region, where the microstructural design can consist of either the single-resonator or the dual-resonator design, to exhibit negative effective mass density.

Each metamaterial unit cell is explicitly modeled with springs and undeformable rigid masses. An impact pulse is given to unit cell #1 and the transient dynamic response of wave propagation, due to the effect of metamaterial region, is analysed before reflection occurs at the right end of the model (unit cell #50). In this simulation, the impact pulse is a prescribed displacement-controlled superposition of two simple harmonic waves ($\omega_1=100$ rad/s and $\omega_2=300$ rad/s), signifying a more complex wave form than a single sinusoidal pulse. The impact pulse has a short duration of around 31.4 ms, as illustrated in Figure 3(b). The model is built using Abaqus CAE and run by Abaqus dynamic explicit.

Figure 4 shows how the microstructural design of metamaterials can affect impact stress wave propagation. The transient and dynamic response of the model is analysed using numerical simulation. Figure 4 portrays time snap-shot of the wave propagation from left to right. When there is no internal resonator in the material (unit cells #21 to #30 containing no internal mass), meaning that the material is not a metamaterial, it is clear that the impact wave passes through the material without any influence and attenuation, as depicted in Figure 4(a). In this study, the material properties (unit cell mass and

spring stiffness) throughout various sections of the model, like Medium 1, Metamaterial and Medium 2 [Figure 3(a)], are kept the same, so as to neglect the effect of impedance mismatch of different materials, focusing the study only on the effect of negative effective mass density due to internal resonator design.

Figure 3: (a) One-dimensional spring-mass lattice system, (b) impact pulse used in simulation.

Figure 4: Impact wave propagation through a (a) non-metamaterial barrier, (b) metamaterial barrier.

In Figure 4(b), the performance of a dual-resonator metamaterial is evaluated. Once again, it is clear that the wave propagation snap-shots at time $t=0.0290$ s and $t=0.0374$ s are the same as that of the non-metamaterial [Figure 4(a)], since the wave has not reached the metamaterial. However, at $t=0.0474$ s, it is evident that there is a significant decrease in the amplitude of the wave form, thus inferring a significant attenuation of stress wave in the metamaterial. It is also evident that very little amount of stress wave passes through beyond the metamaterial. In fact, there is a significant amount of reflection from the metamaterial. In this case, the dual-resonator metamaterial works well and is able to effectively attenuate the input excitation wave that spans over 2 broad frequencies. In transient impact loading, internal resonators have demonstrated to be effective in reducing the displacement of the protected structure (Medium 2 in this study), and attenuate a specifically-designed range of frequency where the negative effective mass density is exhibited.

3.2 Blast Wave Mitigation

To demonstrate blast-wave mitigation, an extended 1D spring-mass lattice system consisting of 400 unit cells is used. To model the elastic metamaterial region, internal resonators (using single-resonator or dual-resonator model) are placed inside the 51st to 60th unit cells to exhibit the effect of negative effective mass density and to mitigate blast-wave propagation. Each metamaterial unit cell is explicitly modeled with springs and undeformable rigid masses. As such, Medium 1 will consist of the first 50 unit cells, and Medium 2 is made up of the remaining unit cells (from unit cell #60 to #400), beyond the metamaterial region. It is well known that blast loading produced by detonation of an explosive is characterised by a very short time duration and extremely sudden and high load peak. In this simulation, the force-controlled blast pulse [Figure 5(a)] is given to unit cell #1 as the input forcing history, based on the following equation:

$$F = F_{\max} e^{-\frac{t-t_0}{t_d}} \quad t \geq t_0 \quad (13)$$

$$F = 0 \quad t < t_0$$

where $F_{\max} = 1,000$ N, $t_0 = 0.5$ ms, $t_d = 0.1$ ms.

Due to the blast pulse, the stress wave generated in the model has a wide frequency domain ranging from 0 to 5,000 Hz, as displayed in Figure 5(b). The frequency spectrum is calculated using Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) by analysing the velocity profile of the 100th unit cell (#100), so as to study the effect of the negative effective mass density of metamaterials on frequency attenuation in blast-wave mitigation. The model is similarly constructed using Abaqus CAE and run on Abaqus dynamic explicit.

Figure 5: (a) Impact blast pulse used in simulation, (b) frequency domain of blast simulation calculated by Fast Fourier Transform (FFT).

The frequency domain (obtained by FFT) of the lattice system subjected to a blast pulse is analysed to understand how specially designed microstructural internal resonator can affect blast-wave mitigation of specific frequency ranges. In Figure 6, we can see the effect of frequency range and the influence of the number of internal resonators. Notations for various cases are explained as follow: “10-500Hz- $\theta=1$ ” represents the case with 10 unit cells (#51 to #60) whereby each unit cell has a single internal resonator of $m_2=0.03\text{kg}$ and $k_2=296088\text{ N/m}$, hence resulting in a designed resonator local frequency of $\omega_2=500\text{ Hz}$, and since $m_2=m_1=0.03\text{kg}$, the mass ratio $\theta= m_2/m_1=1$ (m_1 is the mass of each outer unit cell, as shown in Figure 1). Figure 6 also compares cases 1-500Hz- $\theta=1$ and 1-1500Hz- $\theta=1$ whereby only 1 unit cell (#51) has an internal resonator. In the cases where the targeted frequency is at 1500Hz, only the spring stiffness of the internal resonator is changed ($k_2=2664793\text{ N/m}$), keeping m_2 and the mass ratio θ the same.

From Figure 6, it is evident that there are dips in the amplitude of the frequency spectrum at specific frequency ranges. These dips, in fact, correspond to the local frequency of the internal resonators accordingly, at 500Hz and 1500Hz in this study. It is clear that the results of the frequency domain plot (Figure 6) reflect the analytical results of the negative effective mass density of the metamaterial (Figure 2). As mentioned previously, the effective mass density of the metamaterial becomes negative at the asymptotic region near the local resonance frequency of the internal mass m_2 when $\omega/\omega_2=1$. This means that waves at these frequency ranges ($1 < \omega/\omega_2 \leq 1.3$, when $\theta=1$) are unable to propagate through the material. As such, from the analytical model (Figure 2), the negative mass region when $\theta=1$ and $\omega_2=500\text{Hz}$ is $500\text{Hz} < \omega \leq 650\text{Hz}$. This corresponds very well with the case 10-500Hz- $\theta=1$. However, for the case of 1-500Hz- $\theta=1$, we can only observe a very sharp dip near 500Hz, where the mass negativity is most paramount. This reveals that having more internal resonators can effectively broaden the frequency range of the wave attenuation, due to more kinetic energy absorbed by more internal resonators. For the cases at higher designed local frequency of the internal resonators (1500Hz), there seems to be wave attenuation over a wider frequency range. This is because when $\theta=1$, the condition that $1 < \omega/\omega_2 \leq 1.3$ remains, thus when $\omega_2=1500\text{Hz}$, the negative mass region naturally extends over $1500\text{Hz} < \omega \leq 1950\text{Hz}$.

Figure 6: Frequency domain (by FFT) showing the effect of frequency range and number of resonators.

Figure 7 evaluates the wave attenuation performance between the dual-resonator model and a double-layered single-resonator model. The detailed parameters of the internal resonators can be found in [6]. It is clear that wave attenuation frequency ranges of these two models are comparable. This implies that the dual-resonator model is more effective, as it requires fewer unit cells (outer mass) to achieve similar efficiency as a double-layered single-resonator model. This also means that by using a dual-resonator model, the metamaterial will be resultantly thinner and thus lighter. The mass saving is

primarily due to the use of lesser outer unit cells. If we try to further reduce the mass of outer unit cells in the double-layered single-resonator model by half ($m_j=0.015\text{kg}$), so that the total mass is the same as that of the dual-resonator model, it is observed that a broader frequency range is being attenuated. This is because by reducing the outer mass, the mass ratio θ is sequentially increased, resulting in wider negative mass region (Figure 2). The same broader band gap can be attained by similarly reducing the outer mass of the dual-resonator model. This again concludes that the dual-resonator model is always thinner and lighter than the double-layered single-resonator model of the same wave attenuation performance.

Figure 7: Frequency domain (by FFT) showing the effect of dual-resonator and reduced outer-mass.

4 DESIGN AND MANUFACTURE OF METACOMPOSITES PROTECTION SYSTEM

In this section, we present a summary and outlook of practical ways to design and manufacture elastic metamaterials with negative effective mass density. Depending on the size of its “microstructure,” a metamaterial may be viewed as macroscopic structure rather than a conventional material. The designs are analogous to the analytical mass-in-mass model described in this paper, whereby an internal resonator exists inside an outer mass. A possible metamaterial with negative effective mass density may be constructed in the form of a composite material consisting of periodic mass-in-mass microstructures embedded in a matrix material [16].

The composites that Liu et al. [17] used have a simple microstructural unit consisting of a solid core material with a relatively high density and a coating of elastically soft material. In their experiments, they used centimeter-sized lead balls as the core inner mass material (internal mass m_2), coated with a 2.5mm layer of silicone rubber (spring k_2). The coated spheres are then arranged in simple cubic crystal structure with epoxy as the hard matrix material (outer mass m_1). Lai et al. [18] further proposes a realistic elastic metamaterial unit that is designed according to the physical model whereby the internal mass is made of steel (m_2), coated with soft silicone rubber (k_2) and embedded within a foam host (m_1). Chen et al. [19] has used physical spring-mass resonators in a sandwich beam to build specimens with negative effective mass density so as to attenuate wave propagation within the band gaps. In their case, internal mass m_2 and spring k_2 can be designed accordingly within the unit resonator cell casing and outer mass m_1 is the sandwich foam core. In the recent work done by Manimala et al. [20], negative effective mass structures are made up of resonators which are of the coil spring-mass type and the outer structure is made of polycarbonate (outer mass m_1) with a guide rod to give lateral support to the resonator mass. It was also found that cantilever beams can be used in place of coil springs to reduce the size of the negative mass structure. Another way to manufacture elastic metamaterial is by using multi-material 3D printing technique to create complex microstructure

generating the same negative effective mass property. Reports regarding on-going work will soon be published.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have explored the use of elastic metamaterials to build a metacomposites protection system that can mitigate dynamic loads and attenuate blast wave. The concept of elastic metamaterials is introduced by presenting the unique property of negative effective mass density through simple analytical mass-in-mass models. Computational simulations demonstrated the impact wave attenuation and blast wave mitigation capability of the metacomposites. Finally, practical ways to design and manufacture metacomposites protection system with negative effective mass density are proposed and presented.

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